

حضرت امام غزالیؒ کی فقہی خدمات کا تحقیقی جائزہ

A RESEARCH REVIEW OF IMAM GAZALI'S JURISPRUDENTIAL SERVICES

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ABSTRACT

Islam is a noble religion and all the Prophets of Allah from Adam to Muhammad (ﷺ) came to this universe with the message of almighty Allah for proper guidance of mankind continuously.

After death of our beloved Prophet Muhammad (ﷺ) almighty Allah has send many honorable literate persons and Islamic scholars (Ulma-e-Islam) for the betterment and proper guidance of Muslim Ummah. Since fifth century till to now there are so many Islamic scholars are available who are agreeing with the different thoughts of Imam Ghazali.

Imam Ghazali continued to stand on his mother religion Islam but he always continued to do research without any hesitation and enquired about new things and invited other scholars to do research and think more and more fare and freely.

The religious and Islamic books were in the study of Imam Ghazali such as Quran, Hadith, Islamic Law and Tasawuf all of these books are main sources for clarification of reality about hereafter life and this life as well.

Therefore in this article the services towards Islamic law of Imam Ghazali have been stated. I am so grateful to almighty Allah for proving me opportunity, courage and ability to write this article.

Keywords: Ghazali, Islamic Teaching, Sharia, Quran, Hadith, Sunnah, Fiqah.

کلیدی الفاظ: غزالی، اسلامی تعلیمات، شریعت، قرآن، حدیث، سنت، فقہ۔

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